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ASSESSMENT OF WATER QUALITY PARAMETERS FOR ESTUARINE AND RIVERINE ZONES OF MAHI RIVER, GUJARAT DURING PRE-MONSOON AND POST-MONSOON SEASON

Ronak Gupta, Ketan Tatu, Lamb Christian, R.D. Kamboj
Gujarat Ecological Education and Research (GEER) Foundation
Indroda Nature Park, P. O. Sector – 7,
Gandhinagar – 382007, Gujarat, India

*Corresponding author Email: lj.jl1517@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The present study had been carried out covering riverine and estuarine areas of Mahi river, which is one of the major rivers that flows through Gujarat. The water samples were collected from selected sites from March 2017 to February 2018 in order to assess seasonal variation in water quality parameters. A total of nine physico-chemical parameters of water were tested and the following results were obtained: pH (6.00 to 8.90), Temperature (16.30 °C to 35.60 °C), Turbidity (41 NTU to 861 NTU), Electrical Conductivity (4.20 mS to 94.72 mS), Total Dissolved Solids (2.23 ppt to 52.8 ppt), Dissolved Oxygen (5.22 mg/l to 9.81 mg/l), Salinity (0.05 ppt to 33.00 ppt), Alkalinity (20 mg/l to 290 mg/l) and Total Hardness (380 mg/l to 6030 mg/l). The results showed that the water quality gets affected by the discharge of industrial effluents and other non-point sources of pollution.

Keywords: Estuarine Zone, Mahi, Physico-Chemical parameters, Riverine Zone, Seasonal sampling, Water quality

Introduction

Estuaries are semi-enclosed bodies of brackish water where freshwater from rivers or streams merges with the open sea. Estuaries harbour highly diverse floral and faunal communities due to mixing of waters having different salt concentrations and variable physical characteristics. Estuaries provide crucial links to nearby ecosystems (Mc Lusky and Elliott, 2004). However, estuaries can suffer from severe pollution impacts due to introduction of a wide variety of chemical contaminants resulting from rapid population growth and unsustainable development in many coastal areas worldwide. Many of the chemical substances are known to concentrate in estuarine waters, or accumulate in estuarine sediments (McCain et al., 1988). One of the main emphasis of estuary research is to study the effects of pollution. Pollutants enter estuaries through storm drains, industrial discharges, run off from lawns, streets, and farmlands; discharges from sewage treatment plants, and atmospheric deposition. Estuaries can be affected by contamination in the following major ways: oxygen depletion (e.g. hypoxia, anoxia) (Saiz Salinas, 1997), toxic substances accumulation or bioaccumulation (e.g. toxic organic

compounds, petroleum products, and heavy metals) (Bryan and Langston, 1992), spills (e.g. oil spills), pathogens (e.g. from sewage) (Lipp et al., 2001), and thermal pollution (e.g. heated effluent from power plants) (Keser et al., 2005). This ecosystem is of great significance from ecological and economical perspectives as it provides habitats and resources for the development of biodiversity. Hence, it is essential to monitor their water quality in order to know the change in various water quality parameters which would be helpful in effective management and conservation of estuarine ecosystem. Therefore, the present study was carried out at selected estuarine and riverine sites of Mahi river in Gujarat during pre-monsoon and post-monsoon seasons.

Study Area

Fig.1: Sampling sites covering estuarine and riverine zones of the Mahi river, Gujarat State

Mahi is one of the major rivers passing through the Gujarat state. It is 583 km long covering 34,842 km of drainage surface area. Mahi Kanta hills in the Vindhya range of Madhya Pradesh is the origin of this river. The River basin spreads over in different states i.e. Rajasthan, Madhya Pradesh and Gujarat (Pandya, 2011). The estuarine stretch extends up to 50 km through Anand, Vadodara and Bharuch districts starting from Fajalpur to Kamboi and it meets the sea at northern part of the Gulf of Khambhat near Kamboi at Kavi. River area near

Mohammad pura village has presence of a rocky sill which prevents the intrusion of salt water beyond this point except during the spring tide. Mahi estuary has a chain of shallow brackish water lagoons and swamps rich in aquatic life. The industrial waste water generated by IPCL, GSFC, Gujarat refinery, GIDC, Indian Dye stuff (P) Ltd. is discharged in Mahi river through the Vadodara effluent channel and the discharge point of Common Effluent Channel is bringing effluents from Dhanora and discharged into the Gulf of Khambhat. According to the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) report the industries in and around Vadodara have been dumping huge quantities of toxic chemicals into Mahi river and Gulf of Khambhat (Sajish, 2012; Pandya, 2011). Hydro Power stations are located along Mahi river at Bajaj Sagar dam and at Kadana Dam. Vadodara is the only important urban center in the basin.

Methodology

Stratified random sampling was used for collection of water samples from ten selected sites for the time span of twelve months ranging from March 2017 to February 2018. The water samples were collected from 10 selected sites during high tide and low tide (Table 1). Among these 10 sites, 8 sites were present in estuarine zone whereas 2 sites were present in the riverine zone. The estuarine and riverine zones were demarcated based on the extent of tidal influence. The water quality parameters such as pH, Temperature, Dissolved Oxygen, Total Dissolved Solids, Conductivity, and Turbidity were assessed *insitu* whereas the remaining parameters were performed *exsitu* at GEER Foundation's laboratory.

For *exsitu* parameters, the water samples were collected in pre-cleaned 1 litre polyethylene bottles, stored in ice box at -4°C and brought to the Laboratory for analysis. The water samples were then analyzed as per the standard methodology (APHA, 2005). In order to know seasonal variation in water quality parameters two seasons were taken into consideration i.e. winter (November 2017 to February 2017) and summer (March 2017 to Mid-June 2017).

Results and Discussion

A total of 9 physico-chemical parameters were analyzed during the study period.

Physical parameters

Water temperature

Fig.2a: Seasonal variation in water temperature at selected sites during high tide

Fig.2b: Seasonal variation in water temperature at selected sites during low tide

The water temperature is a significant parameter as it regulates various abiotic characteristics and biotic activities of an aquatic ecosystem (Radhika *et al.*, 2004). In present study, the water temperature at various sites varied from 16.30°C to 35.60°C. The highest water temperature (i.e. 35.60°C) was recorded at Badalpur (N 22° 15' 26.6" E 72° 47' 53.4") during

high tide in summer. On the other hand, the lowest water temperature (i.e. 16.30°C) was recorded at Sarod (N 22° 11' 06.4", E 72° 42' 52.5") in winter during low tide. Average value of water temperature for summer and winter seasons during high tide was 28.80°C and 24.10°C, respectively (Fig. 2a & 2b). On the other hand, average value of water temperature recorded during low tide for summer and winter was 26.95°C and 22.26°C respectively (Table 2). The results were found to be in similar to those derived through investigations carried out by Martin *et al.* (2008) for Cochin estuary of South India, where they reported a temperature variation of 28 °C to 32 °C during pre-monsoon period. Higher temperature was observed during summer due to clear atmosphere, greater solar radiation and low water level. The change in water temperature may be attributed to the change in solar radiation received in different seasons along the study sites (Ozaki *et al.*, 2003).

Turbidity

Fig.3a: Seasonal variation in turbidity at selected sites during high tide

Fig.3b: Seasonal variation in turbidity at selected sites during low tide

Turbidity is a measure of water clarity and the main sources of turbidity are erosion, living organisms and human activities. During the study period, turbidity at various sites varied from 41 NTU to 861 NTU. The highest turbidity (i.e. 861 NTU) was recorded at Badalpur (N 22° 15' 26.6", E 72° 47' 53.4") during high tide in summer. On the other hand, the lowest turbidity (i.e. 41 NTU) was recorded at Chokari (N 22° 14' 30.6", E 72° 55' 20.5") in summer during low tide (Fig. 3a & 3b). Average values of turbidity for summer and winter seasons during high tide were 391.70 NTU and 301.53 NTU respectively. On the other hand, average values of turbidity recorded for all the sites during low tide condition for summer and winter were 273.31 NTU and 258.88 NTU respectively (Table 2). The values of turbidity were higher near estuarine region which might be due to influx of high amount of sediments and other materials carried by Mahi river. The trend line also shows that turbidity increases towards the estuarine region.

Chemical parameters

pH

Fig.4a: Seasonal variation in pH at selected sites during high tide

Fig.4b: Seasonal variation in pH at selected sites during low tide

The pH is one of the very significant chemical characteristic of all waters, which explains certain significant biotic and abiotic ecological characteristics of aquatic systems in general. The pH of a water body is a diurnally variable property according to temperature variation in the system (Ojha & Mandloi, 2004). During the study period the pH at all the sampling sites varied from 6.00 to 8.90. The highest pH (i.e. 8.90) was observed at Chokari (N 22° 14' 30.6", E 72° 55' 20.5") in winter during low tide, whereas the, lowest pH (i.e. 6.00)

was observed at Chokari (N 22° 14' 30.6", E 72° 55' 20.5") in summer during low tide (Fig. 4a & 4b). Average value of pH recorded for summer and winter was 7.96 and 7.82, respectively during high tide. On the other hand, the average value of pH recorded during low tide condition for summer and winter was 7.17 and 7.58, respectively (Table 2). Due to the buffering capacity of the sea water, generally, the pH ranges from 7.8 to 8.3 in estuaries (Millero, 1986). Significant changes in pH occur due to disposal of industrial wastes, acid mine drainage etc. Such changes can make many common pollutants more toxic. In natural waters pH also changes diurnally and seasonally due to variation in photosynthetic activity which increases the pH due to consumption of carbon dioxide in the process. Prakash *et al.* (2009) observed a wide range in pH change from 6.9 to 8.8 during monsoon to pre-monsoon period in tropical Cauvery river system.

Electrical Conductivity

Fig.5a: Seasonal variation in Electrical Conductivity at selected sites during high tide

Fig.5b: Seasonal variation in Electrical Conductivity at selected sites during low tide

The EC of water is due to ionization of dissolved inorganic solids and is a measure of total dissolved solids and salinity (Bhatt *et al.*, 1999). The values of Electrical conductivity in present study, ranged from 4.20 mS to 94.72 mS. The highest EC (i.e. 94.72 mS) was recorded at Dabka (N 22° 15' 00.8", E 72° 57' 29.5") during High tide in winter season. On the other hand, the lowest EC (i.e. 4.20 mS) was recorded at Tithor (N 22° 13' 10.9", E 72° 52' 16.9") in winter during high tide (Fig 5a & 5b). Average value of EC recorded during high tide for summer and winter was 33.21 mS and 40.08 mS respectively. On the other hand, average value of EC recorded during low tide condition for summer and winter was 22.99 mS and 35.68 mS respectively (Table 2). Which might be due to the influence of fresh water in some of the study sites of Mahi Estuary.

Total Dissolved solids

Fig.6a: Seasonal variation in Total Dissolved Solids at selected sites during high tide

Fig.6b: Seasonal variation in Total Dissolved Solids at selected sites during low tide

Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) in water consist of inorganic salts and dissolved materials. In natural waters, salts are chemical compounds of anions such as carbonates, chlorides, sulphates, nitrates, and cations such as potassium, magnesium, calcium, and sodium

(Arockia and Lakshmanan, 2014). During the study period, TDS at various sites were found to be ranged from 2.23 ppt to 52.80 ppt. The highest TDS (i.e. 52.80 ppt) was recorded at Dabka (N 22° 15' 00.8", E 72° 57' 29.5") during high tide in winter, whereas, the lowest TDS (i.e. 2.23 ppt) was recorded at Tithor (N 22° 13' 10.9", E 72° 52' 16.9") in winter during high tide (fig 6a & 6b). Average value of TDS recorded during high tide for summer and winter was 21.23 ppt and 17.59 ppt, respectively. On the other hand, average value of TDS recorded during low tide condition for summer and winter was 13.20 ppt and 18.43 ppt, respectively (Table 2).

Dissolved oxygen

Fig. 7a: Seasonal variation in Dissolved oxygen at selected sites during high tide

Fig. 7b: Seasonal variation in Dissolved oxygen at selected sites during low tide

The Dissolved oxygen (DO) reflects the water quality status and physical and biological processes in waters and shows the metabolic balance of the organisms in a water body. The DO is an important water quality parameter in assessing water pollution (Laluraj *et al.*, 2002). During the present study Dissolved Oxygen at various sites varied from 5.22 mg/l to 9.81 mg/l. The highest DO (i.e. 9.81 mg/l) was recorded at Dhuvaran (N 22° 14' 06.5", E 72° 45' 54.5") during low tide in winter. On the other hand, the lowest DO (i.e. 5.22 mg/l) was recorded at Badalpur (N 22° 15' 26.6", E 72° 47' 53.4") in summer during high tide (Fig 7a & 7b). Average value of DO recorded during high tide for summer and winter was 6.24 mg/l and 7.50 mg/l, respectively. On the other hand, average value of DO recorded during low tide condition for summer and winter was 6.34 mg/l and 7.97 mg/l respectively (Table 2).

Sankar *et al.* (2010) while working on coastal waters of Uppanar estuary reported dissolved oxygen level of 2.8 to 5.5 mg/l. The higher dissolved oxygen present in the upper reaches of Mahi estuary might be due to the freshwater influence in these areas. The DO in lower estuarine mouth of Mahi estuary was recorded 0.6 mg/l only. Similar observations were recorded by Roegner *et al.* (2011) while working on Columbia river estuary. They suggested that low concentration of dissolved oxygen at the estuarine mouth may be attributed to wind stress, tidal stress and ocean forcing. The lowest DO values were observed during the pre-monsoon period of present study. High biological activity during pre-monsoon period may be responsible for low dissolved oxygen concentration in estuaries as observed in Chesapeake Bay (Levinton, 2001). The lower dissolved oxygen concentration reported at lower reaches of Mahi estuary during summer season might also be due to the domestic as well as industrial effluent released into the region as these are the main source of oxidisable organic matter (Abdullahi *et al.*, 2008).

Salinity

Fig.8a: Seasonal variation in Salinity at selected sites during high tide

Fig.8b: Seasonal variation in Salinity at selected sites during low tide

Salinity is a direct measure of the amount of salts in the water. Salinity influences several processes such as dissolution, dispersion and dilution in sea water due to high dissolved salt content and higher density (Sajish, 2012). In the study, salinity at various sites was found

ranging from 0.05 ppt to 33.00 ppt. The highest Salinity (i.e. 33.00 ppt) was recorded at Kavi (N 22° 13' 01.4", E 72° 36' 59.1") during high tide in winter season and the lowest Salinity (i.e. 0.05 ppt) was recorded at Dabka (N 22° 15' 00.8", E 72° 57' 29.5") in winter during low tide (Fig 8a & 8b). Average value of salinity recorded during high tide for summer and winter were 7.78 ppt and 14.70 ppt, respectively. On the other hand, average value of salinity during low tide for summer and winter were 4.75 ppt and 16.50 ppt, respectively (Table 2). Satpathy *et al.* (2009) recorded the salinity ranging from 23.4 ‰ to 35.9 ‰ in Kalpakkam Coast of South east India and the highest being recorded during pre-monsoon season which corroborates with the finding of present study. The trend line in the graph also reveals that the salinity values increases towards estuarine region which is due to increased concentration of salts present in estuarine waters.

Alkalinity

Fig. 9a: Seasonal variation in Alkalinity at selected sites during high tide

Fig. 9b: Seasonal variation in Alkalinity at selected sites during low tide

Alkalinity of water is its capacity to neutralize a strong acid and is characterized by presence of all hydroxyl ions capable of combining with hydrogen ions (Koshy & Nayar,

2000). Alkalinity is used as criteria for determining the nutrient status of waters (Moyle, 1949). During the study period, alkalinity at various sites varied from 290 mg/l to 290 mg/l. The highest alkalinity (i.e. 290.00 mg/l) was recorded at Jaspur (N 22°18' 01.4", E 73° 02' 42.6") during low tide in winter. On the other hand, the lowest alkalinity (i.e. 20 mg/l) was recorded at Kavi (N 22° 13' 01.4", E 72° 36' 59.1") in summer during low tide (Fig. 9a & 9b). Average value of alkalinity recorded during high tide for summer and winter were 39 mg/l and 47 mg/l, respectively. However, average values of alkalinity recorded during low tide condition for summer and winter were 33.75 mg/l and 90 mg/l, respectively (Table 2). Meera & Nandan (2010) on their study on Valanthakad backwaters of Kerala suggested that low alkalinity value at post-monsoon may be attributed to increased uptake or release of carbon dioxide by organisms there by changing the proportion of carbonate and bicarbonate ions in water.

Total Hardness

Fig. 10a: Seasonal variation in Total Hardness at selected sites during high tide

Fig. 10b: Seasonal variation in Total Hardness at selected sites during low tide

Total Hardness of water is mainly due to the presence of calcium and magnesium ions, and it is an important indicator of the toxic effect of poisonous elements (Tiwari, 2001). The Total Hardness at various sites varied from 200.00 mg/l to 8600.00 mg/l. during entire study the highest Total Hardness (i.e. 8600.00 mg/l) was recorded at Dhuvaran (N 22⁰ 14' 06.5", E 72⁰ 45' 54.5") during high tide in summer. Whereas the, lowest Total Hardness (i.e. 200.00 mg/l) was recorded at Rajupura (N 22⁰ 28' 11.0", E 73⁰ 05' 20.6") in summer (Fig 10a & 10b). Average value of Total Hardness recorded during high tide for summer and winter were 3843.80 mg/l and 2440.50 mg/l, respectively. On the other hand, average values of Total Hardness recorded during low tide condition for summer and winter were 4325.00 mg/l and 2201.25 mg/l, respectively (Table 2). Similar observations were reported by Prasanna & Ranjan (2010) in Dhamra estuary with the Total Hardness values of 969.68 mg/l to 5655.24 mg/l.

Conclusion

In the present study various physico-chemical parameters of estuarine and riverine waters of the Mahi river were monitored. It was found that the values of some physico-chemical characteristics like Total Hardness, Turbidity and Total Dissolved Solids at few estuarine sites (viz. Jaspur, Dabka, Chokari, Tithor, Badalpur, Dhuvaran, Sarod and Kavi) were above the values of the maximum permissible limit for domestic water quality as per IS 10500 – 2004. The major source of pollution in Mahi estuary may include anthropogenic activities, agricultural run-off and industrial effluents. It is recommended that domestic sewage, agriculture run-off and industrial effluents must be treated before discharging them into Mahi river and its estuary at Gulf of Khambhat.

Acknowledgements

The authors are thankful to the Forests and Environment Department, Govt. of Gujarat state for providing financial support under the project Ecological monitoring of estuaries of major rivers of Gujarat. For carrying out this study. Authors also appreciate the support of Mr. Vikram Singh, Manager Projects. The support of other research staff and laboratory staff of GEER Foundation for field data collections and sample analyses are duly acknowledged.

Table 1. Water sampling sites on Mahi River

SN	Village	Latitude (N)	Longitude (E)	Type of site
1	Rajpur	22 ⁰ 28' 11.0''	73 ⁰ 05' 20.6''	Riverine*
2	Fajalpur	22 ⁰ 26' 03.5''	73 ⁰ 04' 22.3''	Riverine*
3	Jasipur	22 ⁰ 18' 01.4''	73 ⁰ 02' 42.6''	Estuarine
4	Dabka	22 ⁰ 15' 00.8''	72 ⁰ 57' 29.5''	Estuarine
5	Chokri	22 ⁰ 14' 30.6''	72 ⁰ 55' 20.5''	Estuarine
6	Tithor	22 ⁰ 13' 10.9''	72 ⁰ 52' 16.9''	Estuarine
7	Badalpur	22 ⁰ 15' 26.6''	72 ⁰ 47' 53.4''	Estuarine
8	Dhuvaran	22 ⁰ 14' 06.5''	72 ⁰ 45' 54.5''	Estuarine
9	Sarod	22 ⁰ 11' 06.4''	72 ⁰ 42' 52.5''	Estuarine
10	Kavi	22 ⁰ 13' 01.4''	72 ⁰ 36' 59.1''	Estuarine

Table 2. Average values of Various Physico Chemical Parameters During High tide and Low tide during Summer and Winter season

SN	Parameters	Average Value			
		High Tide		Low Tide	
		Summer	Winter	Summer	Winter
1	Water Temperature (°C)	28.80	24.10	26.95	22.26
2	Turbidity (NTU)	391.70	301.53	273.31	258.88
3	pH	7.96	7.82	7.17	7.58
4	Electrical Conductivity (mS)	33.21	40.08	22.99	35.68
5	Total Dissolved Solids (mg/l)	21.23	17.59	13.20	18.43
6	Dissolved Oxygen (mg/l)	6.24	7.50	6.34	7.97
7	Salinity (ppt)	7.78	14.70	4.75	16.50
8	Alkalinity (mg/l)	39.00	47.00	33.75	90.00
9	Total Hardness (mg/l)	3843.80	2440.50	4325.00	2201.25

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